

Mismatch Between Million Veteran Program Genome-Wide Association Study Summary Statistics and dbSNP Reveals Reference/Alternate Assignment Error

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Technical Comment and Response

The genome-wide association study (GWAS) by Verma et al. (1) is a substantial contribution to the literature. GWASs provide insights into the genetic architecture of disease and guide precision prevention and treatment. Underrepresentation of non-European populations in GWASs raises concerns regarding the generalizability of genetic discoveries. The Million Veteran Program (MVP) addresses this gap by recruiting a large, diverse cohort of individuals of European, Hispanic, African, and Asian ancestry. With more than 635,000 participants, 44 million imputed variants, and detailed phenotypic data linked through electronic health records, the MVP is a key resource for population-scale genetic research. Verma et al. demonstrated that genetic similarities across ancestries outweigh differences, with most variation driven by allele frequency differences. Through the PheWeb platform³ and the release of comprehensive GWAS summary statistics, the MVP enables large-scale cross-population analyses and trait-specific genetic discovery.

When analyzing the publicly released GWAS summary statistics from the associated repository (2), we identified a systematic inconsistency between the reported reference (ref) and alternate (alt) alleles and those in dbSNP Build 153 (3). We also uncovered discrepancies between the summary statistics and the PheWeb portal of Verma et al. (4), such as differences in the REF, ALT, allele frequency, and effect size (BETA)

33 fields. The PheWeb portal data are consistent with those in dbSNP and likely reflect the correct allele
34 orientations.

35 As a representative example, we analyzed approximately 20 million overlapping variants from the
36 summary statistics for the Phe_571 phenotype (chronic liver disease and cirrhosis, European ancestry) and
37 dbSNP Build 153. Similar ref/alt inconsistencies were also observed in other phenotypes, including
38 Phe_433_3, suggesting the inconsistency may affect the entire dataset. We compared the ref and alt fields
39 reported in the summary file against the corresponding dbSNP reference records.

40 Our analysis revealed that:

- 41 • 88.1% of single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) exhibited an inversion between the reported ref and
42 alt alleles (i.e., the ref field matched the dbSNP alt allele and vice versa).
- 43 • Only 0.2% of SNPs matched the dbSNP reference alleles as expected.
- 44 • 11.7% of SNPs exhibited complete mismatches with dbSNP alleles.

45 These findings are summarized in **Figure 1**, and the results for 15 randomly selected SNPs are presented
46 in **Table 1**. **Figure 2** illustrates the deviation in allele frequency consistency caused by this inconsistency,
47 where a clear reversed correlation pattern (from upper left to lower right) is observable.

48 The systematic nature of this inconsistency suggests problems during the generation of the summary
49 statistics, such as strand misalignment or incorrect labeling of allele fields.

50 This inconsistency is not a trivial formatting error, and directly affects the following:

- 51 • Interpretation of reported effect alleles.
- 52 • Directionality of association signals.
- 53 • Validity of downstream applications, such as polygenic risk score calculations and meta-analyses.

54 Without correction, users of the summary dataset may inadvertently reverse the biological meaning of
55 associations, leading to erroneous conclusions. We respectfully bring this observation to the attention of the
56 authors and the broader scientific community. Given the extensive use of large GWAS summary statistics in
57 secondary analyses, we recommend a thorough review of the released data and, if appropriate, an official
58 correction. We also commend Verma et al. for their commitment to data sharing, which enabled this quality
59 control analysis.

60 To support the submission, I have also uploaded the supplementary figures and explanation to Zenodo.

61 The data are available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15558207>

62 **Figure 1. Distribution of Ref/Alt Comparison Outcomes Between Summary Statistics and dbSNP**

63 Bar plot illustrating the number of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) categorized as “Match” (ref and
64 alt alleles in the summary statistics match those in dbSNP), “Flipped” (ref matches dbSNP alt and vice
65 versa), and “Mismatch” (neither allele matches dbSNP) among approximately 20 million overlapping
66 variants analyzed from the MVP Phe_571 summary statistics. The results reveal a systematic inversion
67 pattern, with most (88.1%) SNPs having flipped alleles. This inconsistency suggests a large-scale allele
68 orientation problem in the released dataset.

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70 **Figure 2. Differences in Allele Frequencies Between dbSNP and Million Veteran Program Summary**
71 **Statistics**

72 Scatter plot comparing the effect allele frequencies reported in the Million Veteran Program (MVP) Phe_571
73 summary statistics (European ancestry) against the reference allele frequencies from dbSNP Build 153. Each
74 dot represents one SNP. The ideal diagonal (gray dashed line) indicates perfect concordance. The observed
75 inverse trend, with numerous SNPs deviating from the diagonal and aligning along a descending slope
76 (upper-left to lower-right), is consistent with a systematic Ref/Alt inversion, reinforcing the findings
77 illustrated in Figure 1.

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80 **Table 1. Ref/Alt Comparison Between Million Veteran Program Summary Statistics and dbSNP for 15 Random Single-Nucleotide Polymorphisms**

81 Twenty SNPs were randomly selected from approximately 20 million overlapping variants in the MVP Phe_571 (European) summary and dbSNP Build 153.
 82 Positions (chrom or pos), alleles from the MVP (ref, alt, or ea), allele frequencies (af, case_af or control_af), odds ratios (ors), and p values (pvals) are depicted.
 83 dbSNP alleles and frequency are listed as Ref or Alt and Freq, respectively. The RefAlt_Status column indicates whether the alleles are consistent (match),
 84 inverted (flipped), or inconsistent (mismatch) between sources.

SNP_ID	chrom	pos	MVP							dbSNP_153			RefAlt_Status	
			ref	alt	ea	af	case_af	control_af	or	pval	Ref	Alt		Freq
rs738408	22	43928850	T	C	C	0.7783	0.7109	0.7834	0.6729	0	C	T	0.7378	Flipped
rs9506776	13	22046711	C	T	T	0.3367	0.3384	0.3366	1.022	0.1024	T	C	0.4643	Flipped
rs139012393	8	106870174	C	G	G	0.9968	0.9971	0.9967	1.152	0.07419	G	C	0.9934	Flipped
rs12157831	22	34172234	T	C	C	0.9983	0.9984	0.9983	1.127	0.4728	C	T	0.9661	Flipped
rs60955927	6	159747863	A	G	G	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	1.232	0.3667	G	A	0.9778	Flipped
rs4661178	1	156551492	G	T	T	0.9441	0.9427	0.9442	0.9609	0.06839	T	G	N. A.	Flipped
rs34316680	10	66734229	A	T	T	0.9885	0.9885	0.9885	0.9992	0.9846	T	A	0.9415	Flipped
rs556253434	11	46212152	C	T	T	0.9996	0.9996	0.9996	1.158	0.7025	T	C	0.9996	Flipped
rs75888017	11	2170603	A	G	G	0.9998	0.9998	0.9998	0.906	0.8011	G	A	0.9982	Flipped
rs186521773	1	118362739	A	G	G	0.9996	0.9997	0.9996	1.565	0.05708	G	A	0.9992	Flipped
rs61813631	1	155895251	C	T	T	0.9851	0.9848	0.9851	0.9685	0.4443	T	C	0.9966	Flipped
rs535602139	5	132184240	A	G	G	0.9943	0.9943	0.9943	1.004	0.9612	G	T	0.001597	Mismatch
rs62069787	17	70506202	A	G	G	0.9775	0.9778	0.9775	1.026	0.4345	G	A	0.9946	Flipped
rs4272700	10	27592379	A	T	T	0.7119	0.7107	0.712	0.9956	0.6516	T	A	0.8375	Flipped
rs565984041	3	147500150	A	G	G	0.9997	0.9997	0.9997	0.8868	0.7799	G	A	0.9996	Flipped

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Reference

1. A. Verma *et al.*, Diversity and scale: Genetic architecture of 2068 traits in the VA Million Veteran Program. *Science* **385**, eadj1182 (2024).
2. https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/dbgap/studies/phs002453/phs002453.v1.p1/analyses/HARE/MVP_R4.1000G_AGR.HARE.PheCodes_DigestiveSystem.tar
3. https://ftp.ncbi.nih.gov/snp/archive/b153/VCF/GCF_000001405.38.gz
4. https://phenomics.va.ornl.gov/pheweb/gia/eur/pheno/Phe_571